

Community Verified Land Ownership Using Self-Sovereign Identity and Blockchain: A Framework for Underdeveloped Regions

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Abstract—Secure land rights are fundamental to economic development and social stability, yet in many developing regions formal land titles are incomplete or absent. Decentralized solutions using blockchain have been piloted to create tamper evident land registries, but they can suffer from the "garbage in, garbage out" problem: inaccurate initial records become permanently recorded.

We propose CoVO (Community-Verified Ownership), a framework that integrates self-sovereign identity (SSI) with community validation to produce trustworthy land ownership records. Local validators (e.g., neighbors, elders, or community land committees) use their Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) to issue cryptographic attestations (Verifiable Credentials) for a claimant's land. These attestations are aggregated by a community notary, who issues a final Ownership Credential or optionally (non fungible) token. The blockchain serves only as an immutable audit layer for signatures, timestamps, and revocations, while sensitive data remains off-chain.

By weaving together social consensus and cryptographic proofs, CoVO generates land titles that are both locally trusted and globally verifiable. We describe the framework's design including governance and dispute resolution and analyze its feasibility for regions where formal registries are weak or nonexistent.

Index Terms—Blockchain, Self-Sovereign Identity, Verifiable Credentials, Land Administration, Tokenization, Community Governance, Property Rights, Underdeveloped Regions

I. INTRODUCTION

Secure and transparent land-ownership documentation remains an acute challenge in many developing regions where formal titling is incomplete or absent. Estimates put the value of untitled real estate in the Global South at *trillions of U.S. dollars* in so-called "dead capital"—assets owned by the poor but unusable as collateral because the market cannot recognise the rights that attach to them [1]. Conventional, paper-based registries frequently fail these communities: opaque bureaucracies, rent-seeking, and under-resourcing translate into disputes, tenure insecurity and exclusion from credit markets [2].

In response, technologists and policymakers have explored *decentralised* land-record solutions. Early pilots—such as the Bitfury–Georgia land registry integration and the Factom–Honduras prototype used blockchains to anchor title transactions immutably, deterring on-ledger tampering [3], [4]. Yet a recurrent critique is the "infrastructural promise" problem [5]: technological immutability does not cure upstream

data errors or the social contestation that produces them. Empirical evaluations find that institutional and community acceptance issues often dwarf purely technical challenges.

Parallel to blockchain, *self-sovereign identity* (SSI) architectures, Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs), have matured into an open standard for portable, selectively disclosable digital claims. Early proposals suggest that SSI can let vulnerable groups store and share property claims under their own cryptographic control, without reliance on a centralised registry. Independently, participatory land-governance research stresses the evidentiary power of local knowledge: the "memories of our neighbours" are often the only proof of ownership in customary settings. Turning those small, everyday acts of recognition into digital credentials could bridge the gap between lived reality and formal documentation.

This paper introduces CoVO (*Community-Verified Ownership*), a model that *synergises* SSI with community validation. Landholders first collect VC attestations from local validators, neighbours, elders, elected committee members, who sign with their own DIDs. A community notary then aggregates and countersigns the evidence into a tamper-evident *Ownership Credential*. A permissioned or public blockchain is used only as a verifiable data registry for DID Documents, credential hashes and revocation lists; no sensitive parcel data is put on-chain. CoVO therefore preserves privacy while offering both social legitimacy and global cryptographic verifiability.

We structure the remainder of this article as follows. Section II surveys related work on blockchain land registries, tokenised title systems, SSI-based identity schemes, and participatory mapping tools. Section III revisits foundational concepts: DIDs, VCs, asset tokenisation and community validation. Section IV specifies the CoVO framework and credential workflow in detail. Section V analyses broader implications and limitations, and Section VI concludes with research directions.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Land tenure in underdeveloped regions is characterized by informality, contested boundaries, and limited integration with centralized registries. In response, a growing body of research and practice has emerged around digital land governance systems. Broadly, two dominant approaches can be identified.

The first is **state-driven formalization**, in which governments undertake systematic titling campaigns or digitize existing registries to improve security of tenure. These efforts often leverage Geographic Information Systems (GIS), cadastral surveys, and legal documentation processes. While these systems offer statutory recognition and formal enforceability, they tend to be resource-intensive and vulnerable to corruption, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and limited scalability, especially in rural and underserved areas [6], [7].

The second path has been through **community based land mapping and recognition**, typically led by NGOs or local land committees. These approaches focus on participatory mapping, customary land rights recognition, and locally verified records [8]. They are often faster to deploy and better aligned with social realities but lack formal legal standing. Moreover, the absence of cryptographic security and audit trails can limit their usefulness in disputes or external recognition by institutions such as banks or courts.

Several pilot projects have demonstrated the feasibility of storing land titles or hashes of property records on permissioned or public blockchains. Notable examples include partnerships in countries such as Georgia and Ghana, where government-backed land title data has been anchored on Blockchain for tamper-evidence and transparency [9]. However, these systems often replicate existing **centralized authority models** and depend on institutional control over both the issuance process and the Blockchain infrastructure.

An adjacent stream of work investigates the use of **Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI)** architectures for credential-based systems, where individuals hold verifiable claims issued by trusted entities in digital wallets [10]. Emerging SSI standards such as Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs) allow for peer issued attestations that can be cryptographically verified without centralized intermediaries [11]. Projects like Kiva Protocol have explored SSI models for financial inclusion, linking identity and land ownership credentials to mobile-first platforms [12]. These systems demonstrate the feasibility of decentralized credential issuance in constrained environments, but there remains a gap in adapting these models to land claims rooted in informal or customary recognition.

Finally, a body of work explores **tokenized real estate**, where land rights are represented as digital tokens (e.g., NFTs) on public blockchains. While this model introduces liquidity and programmability, it typically presumes the existence of clear ownership rights and enforceable contracts. In contexts lacking legal titles, tokenization risks reinforcing elite control or creating parallel systems with limited community input.

This paper proposes a third path: combining community based land recognition with SSI based credentialing in a model we call **Community-Verified Ownership (CoVO)**. This approach centers local knowledge and decentralized validation while leveraging modern identity and credential standards for verifiability and scalability.

A particularly relevant contribution is [13], which presents a decentralized framework for real estate transfer verification

using self-sovereign identity (SSI) and smart contracts. Their work demonstrates how Verifiable Credentials can be used to assert ownership claims and automate transfer logic through decentralized trust workflows. However, their model focuses on bilateral interactions and programmable logic rather than incorporating structured community governance or multi-tier validation processes. CoVO builds upon this by introducing a collective endorsement structure, enabling social verification of land claims before formal issuance.

III. TECHNICAL PRELIMINARIES

The design of a decentralized, community-oriented land credentialing framework draws upon several foundational technologies and conceptual models: Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs), Verifiable Credentials (VCs), tokenization mechanisms (e.g., non-fungible tokens), and the role of social trust in validation processes.

A. Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs)

Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) are a class of globally unique identifiers designed to be self-owned and resolvable without relying on a centralized registry. Each DID is associated with a DID Document that contains cryptographic material (such as public keys) and service endpoints [14]. DIDs can be registered using various DID methods (e.g., `did:web`, `did:key`) that define how the identifier and its metadata are anchored on a blockchain or other decentralized system.

In the context of land administration, DIDs offer a robust and portable mechanism for representing the identity of individuals (e.g., land claimants, validators), organizations (e.g., NGOs or local councils), and entities such as parcels or community committees. They enable each participant in the credentialing process to independently control their cryptographic keys, reducing reliance on third-party identity providers.

B. Verifiable Credentials (VCs)

Verifiable Credentials (VCs) are digitally signed assertions issued by one entity (issuer) about another (subject), conforming to the W3C Verifiable Credentials Data Model [10]. VCs can encapsulate structured claims (e.g., “Alice owns parcel 123”) and include metadata such as issuance time, expiration, and credential status references.

In a land ownership workflow, a VC may represent a property claim, an endorsement by a local validator, or a final certificate of community-recognized ownership. The subject of a VC is typically identified by a DID, and the credential is signed by the issuer using a cryptographic key referenced in their DID Document. Verifiers, such as banks or local governments, can then validate the signature and status of the VC without relying on a centralized registry.

C. Tokenization and Blockchain

Tokenization refers to the digital representation of ownership or rights using on-chain assets, typically non-fungible tokens (NFTs) or asset-backed tokens. While tokenization is

not a prerequisite for verifiability, it can add an additional layer of transparency and transferability.

In a community verification context, a final Ownership VC could be optionally mirrored as a token on a permissioned or public blockchain. The token’s metadata may include a hash of the underlying VC, enabling anchoring and timestamping of the credential without exposing its contents. This design supports interoperability with broader decentralized finance ecosystems, where land tokens could be recognized as collateral or proof of assets provided adequate trust in the underlying credential issuance process exists.

However, tokenization must be approached with caution in informal settings. Issuing tradable tokens without consensus on rightful ownership or proper community validation risks exacerbating land disputes or exclusion. As such, CoVO treats tokenization as an optional extension layer, only to be employed after sufficient community verification.

D. Community Validation and Local Trust Models

Formal land registries often rely on statutory evidence and legal documentation. In contrast, many communities particularly in underdeveloped regions depend on social validation processes: inheritance traditions, collective memory, and oral testimonies of occupancy or transfer.

Community validation refers to the structured involvement of trusted local actors such as elders, land committee members, or neighbors in verifying the legitimacy of land claims. These actors can issue VCs attesting to a claimant’s occupancy, boundaries, or customary rights. Such attestations, when signed using DIDs and presented as VCs, form a cryptographically verifiable chain of trust.

This model is compatible with decentralized identity architectures and aligns with customary practices of consensus-based land recognition. Moreover, by encoding community governance into credential issuance policies (e.g., requiring endorsements from multiple validators or specific roles), the system can prevent single points of failure and promote collective accountability.

The use of DIDs and VCs for off-chain ownership proof has been analyzed in multiple decentralized identity frameworks [15], confirming their suitability for self-sovereign control.

IV. PROPOSED CoVO FRAMEWORK

The Community-Verified Ownership (CoVO) model introduces a decentralized, socially-grounded approach to land rights formalization by integrating decentralized identity (DID) and verifiable credential (VC) standards with community-based validation workflows. Rather than relying on centralized registries or institutional issuers, CoVO derives trust from peer attestations and notary endorsement within a verifiable cryptographic framework. This section outlines the actors, credential types, system architecture, and end-to-end operational flow of the CoVO model.

A. Roles and System Components

CoVO comprises four principal roles: (1) the **Claimant**, who seeks to establish formal recognition of land ownership; (2) a group of **Community Validators**, who issue attestations based on local knowledge or observation; (3) a **Community Notary**, who aggregates endorsements and issues a formal ownership credential; and (4) an external **Verifier**, such as a bank, NGO, or government body, which consumes the credential in downstream use cases.

Each actor is represented by a DID, resolvable via a decentralized ledger-Blockchain. All credentials are managed via a user controlled wallet application that facilitates the creation, receipt, and presentation of verifiable credentials. Importantly, CoVO maintains minimal on-chain data: the Blockchain (public or consortium-based) serves primarily as a registry for DID documents, credential schemas, and optional revocation logs.

Figure 1 depicts the core system architecture and trust relationships. The land owner (claimant) aggregates signed attestation credentials from community validators and submits them to the notary. Upon verifying the endorsements, the notary issues a formal ownership credential, which is then used by the owner in interactions with third parties.

Fig. 1: High-level system architecture of the CoVO model. Solid lines indicate credential issuance; dashed lines represent Blockchain interactions.

B. Credential Structure and Schema Design

Two credential types are central to the CoVO protocol:

- **Community Attestation Credential:** Issued by validators, this credential contains the validator’s DID, the claimant’s DID, a description or identifier of the land parcel (e.g., geocoordinates or local reference ID), and a semantic statement such as “occupies” or “inherits.” Each credential includes standard metadata such as issuance date, expiration, and a cryptographic signature.
- **Ownership Credential (CoVO VC):** Issued by the notary, this credential aggregates endorsements from validators. It may include hashes of the underlying attestation credentials or a summary statement, as well as the parcel identifier and ownership assertion.

All credential schemas are published and versioned on the Blockchain, enabling standardization, reusability, and transparent policy enforcement across communities.

C. Credential Issuance Workflow

Figure 2 illustrates the full lifecycle of credential issuance in the CoVO model, consisting of four discrete steps:

- 1) **Attestation Phase:** The claimant initiates a land claim via their wallet, which generates a VC subject structure referencing the land parcel. Community validators review the claim typically through in-person verification and issue signed attestation VCs.
- 2) **Aggregation Phase:** Once the claimant has gathered sufficient endorsements (e.g., based on a local quorum policy), they submit a verifiable presentation of these credentials to the community notary. The presentation is signed by the claimant and may include additional metadata or supporting evidence.
- 3) **Issuance Phase:** The notary validates the endorsing credentials (e.g., checking issuer DIDs, expiration, and revocation status) and, upon satisfying the predefined criteria, issues the final Ownership VC. The hash of this credential may be anchored on the Blockchain for verifiability.
- 4) **Verification Phase:** The land owner presents the Ownership VC to an external verifier. The verifier checks its cryptographic integrity, verifies the issuer’s DID and policy compliance, and optionally consults the Blockchain for revocation or credential metadata.

Fig. 2: Credential flow in the CoVO model. Numbered steps represent the sequential process of attestation, aggregation, issuance, and verification.

D. Trust Model and Governance

CoVO emphasizes decentralized trust anchored in social legitimacy and cryptographic verifiability. Each validator operates as an independent issuer, and their reputations may be managed through local governance or via a DID-based trust registry. The community notary can be a single trusted entity or a multi-signature group (e.g., 2-of-3 council) having a single DID, aligning with customary decision-making structures and DID controller specification.

V. EVALUATION & DISCUSSION

A. Technical Perspective

By expressing land claims as Verifiable Credentials (VCs), CoVO recasts land administration as an open, credential-based trust network rather than a monolithic database. Because any issuer with a resolvable Decentralised Identifier (DID) can participate, community committees, NGOs and cadastral

agencies can coexist under the same verification logic. This federated architecture offers two benefits. First, it eliminates the single point of failure inherent in central registries; second, it distributes storage and processing costs, making the system attainable for low income regions that cannot finance a national land-information backbone. CoVO also highlights the importance of user-friendly key management in SSI. Landowners in rural areas may have low digital literacy, so expecting them to manage cryptographic keys is a challenge. The implications are that the success of CoVO might depend on innovations in custodial wallets or social key recovery.

B. Socio-Economic Perspective

If widely adopted, CoVO could significantly empower communities in asserting and protecting their land rights. By lowering the barrier to obtaining “proof” of ownership, more individuals could leverage their land assets: for example, as collateral in microfinance or to facilitate land transfers that are consensual. In economic terms, this could help unlock credit for smallholder farmers (one of De Soto’s primary arguments for formalization), albeit in an informal-but-recognized manner. Socially, CoVO might strengthen community institutions: validators and notaries become important roles, which might formalize local governance structures. It gives a framework for communities to take ownership of their own land records, potentially increasing cohesion. However, there is also a flip side: formalizing any rights can lead to external interest, once land has documented value, outside investors or speculators might be more keen to acquire it. Another implication is in disaster or conflict recovery. In many post-conflict settings, formal records are destroyed and people return to land with only community memory as proof. CoVO could be a powerful tool in such contexts: it could rapidly crowdsource the reconstruction of who owns what, in a form that can’t be easily destroyed (since credentials are digital and backed up to a cloud or ledger).

C. Legal Perspective

A CoVO credential is, in its present form, persuasive evidence rather than statutory title. Comparative property law suggests a pathway of *progressive formalisation*, whereby legislation follows community-verified credentials weight and allows administrative conversion to full title once specified endorsement quorums are met. Such hybrid regimes already exist in parts of Latin America and East Africa; integrating CoVO would primarily require procedural, not conceptual adjustments. Until those reforms materialise, the force of a credential is largely social.

D. Governance, Security and Sustainability

On the technical security side, the biggest risk is key compromise: if a validator’s private key is stolen, an attacker could issue fraudulent attestations. Mitigation includes robust practices (hardware wallets, key ceremonies to replace keys if suspected compromised) and the fact that one validator

alone usually can't subvert the system; you'd need to compromise multiple to fool the notary's threshold. Another risk is Blockchain dependence: CoVO's trust in DIDs assumes the Blockchain itself is secure and decentralized. If using a public blockchain, one must ensure transaction costs are affordable for the community. If using a permissioned Blockchain, governance of that Blockchain (who runs the nodes) introduces another layer of trust. For CoVO to have lasting impact, it needs to endure beyond a pilot phase. This implies a sustainable model, possibly integrating with economic incentives. One idea is to incorporate a small fee for credential issuance (much like some customary systems require a token payment to elders when formalizing a sale).

VI. CONCLUSION

We have presented a framework for community-based real estate tokenization aimed at underdeveloped regions, with a focus on creating a verifiable proof of ownership in the absence of reliable formal land registries.

We heeded warnings from studies in land governance that highlighted data integrity and human factors: the real challenges are social, legal, and political, not technical. Our framework directly addresses these by creating a participatory, accountable system that could organically integrate with legal frameworks. We also learned from pilot projects: the Georgian blockchain land-titling taught us the value of government support and the dramatic efficiency gains possible; the Ghanaian and prototype showed how community oversight can prevent fraud; and other emerging initiatives demonstrated the feasibility of tokenizing land assets for social impact. However, unlike many of those, CoVO is not a top-down or one-off solution, it is a model for community adoption.

We acknowledge that significant real-world testing and refinement will be needed. Future work should involve pilot deployments in collaboration with local communities and observers to evaluate the framework's effectiveness. Key performance indicators would include the accuracy of recorded claims, the community's satisfaction and trust in the system (are people using it and recommending it?), and the degree of acceptance by external entities (did banks start lending with land tokens as collateral? did any court cases reference the blockchain records?). Technical research can also improve the framework: for instance, exploring the integration of AI/ML for boundary detection (to assist communities in mapping). Another important area is policy research: engaging with lawmakers to create environments for community-driven land registries.

In conclusion, the CoVO framework aims to enable communities to take charge of their land rights using modern tools, without waiting for top-down reforms. It offers a path to democratize land-tenure security, by turning the community itself into the source of truth for property ownership and logging that truth on an immutable ledger.

REFERENCES

[1] H. de Soto, *The Mystery of Capital: Why Capitalism Triumphs in the West and Fails Everywhere Else*. Basic Books, 2003.

- [2] The World Bank, *Land Policies for Growth and Poverty Reduction: A World Bank Policy Research Report*. Oxford University Press, 2003.
- [3] L. Shin, "Republic of georgia to pilot land titling on blockchain," *Forbes*, April 2016, accessed: 2025-01-01. [Online]. Available: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/laurashin/2016/04/21/republic-of-georgia-to-pilot-land-titling-on-blockchain-with-economist-hernando-de-soto-bitfury/>
- [4] J. Maxim, "Factom partners with honduras government for blockchain land registry," *Bitcoin Magazine*, 2015, accessed: 2025-01-01. [Online]. Available: <https://bitcoinmagazine.com/business/factom-partners-honduras-government-build-blockchain-backed-land-registry-1432065422>
- [5] T. Rodima-Taylor and A. N. Estabrook, "Infrastructural intimacies and the (re)making of customary land tenure," *Land Use Policy*, vol. 101, 2021.
- [6] K. Deininger and H. Selod, "Land registration in developing countries: Insights from experience and research," World Bank, Policy Research Working Paper 4317, 2008.
- [7] V. L. Lemieux, "Trusting records: Is blockchain technology the answer?" *Records Management Journal*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 110–139, 2016.
- [8] M. McDermott. (2020) Participatory land mapping in customary areas: Tools and approaches. USAID LandLinks. [Online]. Available: <https://tenuresecurity.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/USING-PARTICIPATORY-APPROACHES-AND-INNOVATIVE-TECHNOLOGY-TO-EMPOWER-COMMUNITIES-IN-SECURING-THEIR-LAND.pdf>
- [9] V. L. Lemieux, "Blockchain and distributed ledgers as trusted record-keeping systems: An archival theoretic evaluation framework," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 115, pp. 518–528, 2021.
- [10] W3C, *Verifiable Credentials Data Model 1.1*, World Wide Web Consortium, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/TR/vc-data-model/>
- [11] D. Reed, M. Sporny, D. Longley, C. Allen, R. Grant, and M. Sabadello, *Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) v1.0*, W3C, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/TR/did-core/>
- [12] Kiva Protocol. (2019) Digital identity for financial inclusion. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kiva.org/protocol>
- [13] A. Shehu, A. Pinto, and M. E. Correia, "A decentralised real estate transfer verification based on self-sovereign identity and smart contracts," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2207.04459*, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.04459>
- [14] W3C DID Working Group, *Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) v1.0: Core architecture*, World Wide Web Consortium, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/TR/did-core/>
- [15] C. Mazzocca, A. Acar, S. Uluagac, R. Montanari, P. Bellavista, and M. Conti, "A survey on decentralized identifiers and verifiable credentials: Towards a standardized digital identity infrastructure," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.02455*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.02455>